

The AP-1 Square Theory

Arya Pathak

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Abstract

This short paper introduces the AP-1 Square Theory, a simple rule for finding the last two digits of the square of any number ending in 1. The method uses basic addition and works for all positive integers with a final digit of 1. A proof and examples are provided.

1 Introduction

In arithmetic, certain patterns appear in the squares of numbers. The AP-1 Square Theory describes one such pattern for numbers ending in 1. It allows you to determine the last two digits of the square without full multiplication, using only one addition.

2 The Rule

If a number ends in 1, then:

Add the number to the number just before it.

The result gives the last two digits of the square.

3 Examples

- $11 + 10 = 21 \Rightarrow 11^2 = 121 \Rightarrow$ last two digits 21
- $21 + 20 = 41 \Rightarrow 21^2 = 441 \Rightarrow$ last two digits 41
- $51 + 50 = 101 \Rightarrow 51^2 = 2601 \Rightarrow$ last two digits 01
- $91 + 90 = 181 \Rightarrow 91^2 = 8281 \Rightarrow$ last two digits 81

4 Proof

Let the number be $x = 10n + 1$, where n is a whole number.

$$x^2 = (10n + 1)^2 = 100n^2 + 20n + 1$$

The term $100n^2$ ends in 00, so it does not affect the last two digits. The remaining part is:

$$20n + 1 = (10n + 1) + (10n) = x + (x - 1)$$

This sum exactly produces the last two digits of x^2 .